

Weighted Shannon entropy as a quantitative measure of façade pattern regularity

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The article presents an original measure of facade pattern regularity, SVE (Shannon-Variance-Entropy), based on weighted Shannon entropy, which aims to quantitatively describe the internal diversity of a composition. The analysis showed that simply taking into account the distance between elements does not improve the accuracy of the regularity description. The variance of element proportions and angular relationships proved to be key factors, significantly increasing the indicator's consistency with aesthetic perception. The best results were obtained for the composite measure SVE_{DAS} , which combines all three components. This measure shows high consistency with expert assessments and effectiveness in the algorithmic generation of facade patterns. The use of the designated metric as a design parameter enables quantitative control of aesthetics, supporting sustainable design in line with SDG 11.

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Introduction

The aesthetics of urban space, especially the composition of architectural elements on building façades, play a key role in the perception of the quality of the urban environment (Malewczyk et al. 2022a, 2024; Samalavičius 2021). The regularity and geometric order of façades, especially the arrangement of windows, affect not only the visual experience of residents and users of public spaces, but also the sense of order, security and identity of a place (Ezz et al. 2024; Wang & Munakata, 2024). The pursuit of aesthetically pleasing, orderly and visually friendly urban spaces is directly in line with Sustainable Development Goal 11 (SDG 11), which calls for the creation of cities and neighborhoods that are safe, inclusive, sustainable and of high quality. Aesthetics and architectural legibility, including the geometric regularity of façades, support the perceived quality of urban life, a sense of local identity and comfort in the use of public space (Weber et al. 2008).

Despite growing interest in the problem of regularity in the context of the aesthetics of the built environment and its relationship to the broader psychophysical well-being of the users of that environment, there are still objective and unambiguous mathematical tools that would allow quantitative assessment of the geometric ordering of façade pattern. Malewczyk's publication from 2025 responded to this challenge by proposing the first version of an index describing the regularity of patterns, consisting of rectangles (symbolizing windows or façade panels) in a two-dimensional façade space. The author's index $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ corresponds to the entropy of the metric distance between the centers of adjacent compositional elements. Despite very high efficiency in the prediction of the degree of regularity by $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ (correlation of about 93%), in the

author's opinion, there remains some field that needs improvement.

The main objective of this paper is to determine a modified façade pattern regularity measure index (SVE - Shannon-Variance-Entropy), based on the original $H_{(\text{centerdist})}$. The new approach involves the introduction of metric entropy weighting, which should increase the sensitivity of the index to more subtle changes in composition regularity. An additional goal of the paper is to develop a generative algorithm and verify the feasibility of designing a composition by top-down determination of its regularity as a potential tool to support sustainable architectural design in line with SDG 11 goals.

The article is based on two research hypotheses. First, the weighted metric entropy index of the distance between the centers of adjacent compositional elements of a façade design describes the regularity of the design better than pure metric entropy. Second, the determined index of weighted metric entropy can be effectively used as an objective function in façade composition pattern generation algorithms.

This paper attempts to answer four research questions. First, how to mathematically define an optimal function that combines Shannon entropy with measures of spatial variance? Second, what façade composition parameters (sizes of compositional elements, spacing, location) most strongly influence the developed SVE index? Third, how does the SVE index correlate with the regularity of façade patterns, and is this correlation stronger than the original $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ index? Fourth, is it possible to algorithmically generate façade patterns through a top-down determination of the SVE parameter?

This article builds on the earlier study, however, based on an expanded research sample of 343 (original 245) compositions based on 49 residential, multi-family buildings nominated for the 2024 European Union Prize for Contemporary Architecture- Mies

Van der Rohe Award (EU Mies Award 2024) in the 'collective housing' category. A new statistical analysis methodology is also proposed.

The rest of the article presents an analysis of key concepts in the context of the current state of knowledge. The author focuses on measures of regularity in architecture, entropy in terms of information theory in terms of spatial analysis, and a review of ways to algorithmically generate compositions.

Measures of regularity in architecture

In the analysis of architectural forms, quantitative methods to objectively assess their regularity and order have become increasingly important. Research on regularity coefficients of façades focuses, among other things, on the analysis of distances between elements, rhythmicity and the occurrence of repetitive geometric patterns (Stiny & Mitchell 1978; Ilgaz et al. 2025; Med'dahi & Boussora 2021).

Applications of fractal geometry to façade analysis are also increasingly reported in the architectural literature, indicating a link between geometric complexity and the aesthetic and environmental perception of buildings (Bovill 1996; Salingaros 1998). Measures such as fractal dimension or complexity indices have been used to describe the structure of historic urban complexes and modern façades, demonstrating their potential as a tool for assessing the quality of space (Ali & Mustafa 2024; Lee 2014; Katona 2023).

Measures of symmetry and proportion, derived from classical theories of architectural composition (Wittkower 1949), are also an important category of analytical tools.

Symmetry, both mirror and translational, plays an important role in the perception of regularity, as confirmed by psychological research and perceptual theory (Jacobsen 2006; Leder et al. 2004). These works indicate that structures with a high degree of

regularity can be more easily recognized and positively evaluated by space users. A rich literature analysis of the issue of regularity measures in broader contexts was also made in Malewczyk's 2025 article.

Shannon's entropy and its applications

Entropy is a concept that was first introduced in the 19th century in thermodynamics to measure the chaotic nature of systems. In 1948, Claude Shannon also began, through entropy (according to Formula 1), to determine the average amount of information in a message, a concept that is particularly relevant in the context of information theory (Shannon 1948; Fourie 2012).

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^n p_i \times \log_2 p_i$$

Formula 1 Entropy in information theory.

Since its introduction, Shannon's entropy has found widespread use in a variety of fields - including the description of the design process (Krus 2013), medical diagnosis (Benish 2020), and research on the relationship between diversity and aesthetic preferences (Redies et al. 2017; Stanischewski et al. 2020; Stamps 2004). The Shannon global entropy coefficient is also widely used in built environment analysis (Güzelci et al. 2020, 2021; Güzelci & Alacam 2019; Crompton 2012; Stamps 2012, 2014).

Based on metric entropy, which is independent of the length of information, the $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ index was developed (Malewczyk, 2025). It is a measure of the metric entropy of a sequence formed from the absolute distances between the centers of compositional elements (e.g., windows, façade panels) on a building façade. A study of 245 compositions based on 50 buildings nominated for the EU Mies Award 2024 in the 'collective housing' category found a 93% correlation between the $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ index and

objective visual regularity. However, Malewczyk (2025) points out the limitations of the index, which does not consider the magnitude of disturbance, only the presence of disturbance, due to Shannon's entropy property, which is sensitive to variation but not to the magnitude of change. For example, the strings 1,3,7,3,5 and 2,35,192,79,192 have the same entropy, despite markedly different dispersion. Moreover, this indicator does not take into account the size of the compositional elements.

This problem can be solved by weighted entropy, proposed by Guiaşu (1971), which considers not only the probability of events, but also their importance (e.g., significance). An example of its application is in investment risk analysis (Nawrocki and Harding, 1986). Weighted entropy is being developed both theoretically (Ebanks 2010) and practically, including in computer science (Kelbert et al. 2017) and urban scale built environment analysis (Boeing 2019; Huynh 2019; Wang 2018). However, no examples of its application in the analysis of architectural forms using metric entropy have yet been found.

$$H = - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times p_i \times \log_2 p_i$$

Formula 2 Entropy in information theory.

Algorithmic façade generation

Over the past two decades, algorithmic façade generation methods have become an important area of architectural research and experimentation, integrating parametric, optimization, environmental and artificial intelligence approaches. Of key importance is parametric design, which enables dynamic control over the geometry, structure and performance of a façade using tools such as Grasshopper, Ladybug or Octopus (Caetano 2020; Narangerel & Stouffs 2016; Shen 2018; Ramadan 2024). This makes it possible

to simultaneously test and optimize forms for daylighting, shading, natural ventilation, and energy production (Narangerel & Stouffs 2016; Lahmar et al. 2022; Chen & Tang 2024).

In the context of the goals of SDG 11 and the topic of this article, research on the use of algorithmic methods to generate façades with aesthetic quality is particularly relevant. Rezakhani and Kim (2024) used genetic algorithms to optimize façades for aesthetics and visibility while maintaining appropriate sunlight parameters. Alagöz and Jamal (2024) used parametric design strategies in developing kinetic façades, striving for a balance between functionality and aesthetics. Similar issues are also addressed by Mahmoud and Elghazi (2016) and other authors (Engin et al. 2023; Wang, Sun, Shao & He 2024; Wang, Zhang, Zhang, Cui & He 2024; Cudzik 2019; Cudzik & Atasoy 2023; Cesbas et al. 2022).

More recently, there have also been attempts to apply artificial intelligence to the design process, including through the use of the Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) algorithm in the early stages of design (Lin et al. 2025), as well as GAN algorithms to generate façades from images (Yu et al. 2020; Shan & Zhang 2022) and other inputs (Wan et al. 2023). Although these algorithms mainly focus on optimizing selected aspects, such as solarization, material consumption or energy efficiency with aesthetics, none of the publications found attempted to quantitatively encode façade aesthetics.

Materials and method

The present study is an expansion of Malewczyk's 2025 study. To increase the sensitivity of the study, the author partially uses, but also partially expands the original research sample. Modified statistical analysis procedures are also used to improve the quality of the results.

Materials

The study is based on materials, that is, 245 compositions of rectangles symbolizing windows or façade panels, on which the original Malewczyk (2025) study was based. The compositions were based on 50 photographs of multifamily buildings that were nominated in 2024 for the European Union Prize for Contemporary Architecture- Mies van der Rohe Award (EU Mies Award 2024) in the 'collective housing' category. In the original study, photographs were downloaded from the competition organizer's website (<https://miesarch.com/archive>). Basing the composition on examples of architecture nominated for such a prestigious award was to ensure the high quality of the research material.

Methods

Weighted entropy

The original Hcenterdist index in Malewczyk's 2025 study was determined based on metric entropy, which was calculated in a similar way to in the works of Stamps (2004, 2014), Cropmpton (2012), Güzelci (2019, 2021) or Stanischewski (2020). However, in order to increase the sensitivity of the determined index, the theoretical basis of Shannon's concept of weighted metric entropy, which was first written about by Guiaşu in 1971, is proposed. Of relevance to this article, from the perspective of the practical application of weighted entropy, are the works of Boeing (2019), Huynh (2019) and Wang and Zhao (2018). These works, although related to urban problems, make use of the author's important idea of weighted entropy with geometric relations.

Software

The study mainly used Blender version 4.3.2 for macOS. This program was used to create and process the study material and also to run scripts in Python version 3.12. The scripts used in the study used libraries such as bpy, bmesh, random, os, math, csv and io.

Creating compositions

In the original study, 49 two-dimensional compositions were created from photos of buildings nominated for the EU Mies Award 2024 in the 'collective housing' category. For one building, a composition was not created. In a further step, 4 variants were created based on each of the 49 original compositions, which clearly differed from each other and from the original composition in the degree of visual regularity. This was achieved by using such procedures as breaking symmetry, varying the distance between compositional elements, varying compositional elements among themselves and the like. In the end, 49 groups of compositions were formed, each of which had 5 compositions. A total of 245 compositions were created.

The current study uses 245 compositions from Malewczyk's 2025 study (source files available <https://doi.org/10.34808/bemn-rd97>) however, an additional 2 compositions were created within each of the 49 groups. The purpose of creating the additional compositions was to enrich the study sample with specimens that differed in visual regularity in a more subtle way, in order to be able to verify the sensitivity of the new weighted entropy-based indices. In the end, 343 compositions (245 original and 98 new) were collected for the study. The process of creating compositions using a group of 12 compositions as an example is visualized in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 The process of creating new compositions for the study based on the original material from Malewczyk's 2025 study using a group of 12 compositions as an example.

Composition analysis

In the original study, each composition was assigned a numerical value from 1 to 5, which determined the visual regularity of a given composition compared to the other specimens in the group (out of 49 groups). 1 meant the most regular while 5 meant the least regular. These values were coded as the 'REG' indicator. As the number of compositions in the 49 groups increased from 5 to 7 in the current study, the author assigned the new compositions the corresponding REG index values. In the current study, the REG index reaches values from 1 to 7. The higher the value, the more irregular the composition.

Fig. 2 Visualization of the connections determined in the study between the centers of the compositional elements and the angles between the connections.

The study used a script from the original Malewczyk (2015) study (source files

available <https://doi.org/10.34808/bemmn-rd97>) in Python, which was run in the internal Python interpreter in Blender. The script was adapted to the requirements of the current study. The task of the script was to perform mathematical analyses of the compositions. Based on the positions of the vertices of the rectangles forming the compositional patterns, the centers of each rectangle were determined and, further, the connections between the nearest neighboring rectangles. The interior angles formed between the connections of the centers of pairs of rectangles, which converge at a single point, were also determined. A visualization of the center connections and angles based on one of the compositions is shown in Figure 2.

In a further step, the script calculated the distances between the centers of the pairs of closest rectangles according to Formula 3.

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{(cx_i - cx_j)^2 + (cy_i - cy_j)^2}$$

Formula 3. Distances between the centers of pairs of rectangles in the composition.

cx_i, cy_i- coordinates of the center of the i-th rectangle

cx_j, cy_j- coordinates of the center of the j-th rectangle

Further, the script determines the index $H_{centerdist}$ according to Formula 4 - analogous to the way described in the article by Malewczyk (2025), the coefficient of variation ($CV_{distance}$) of distance d_{ij} , according to Formula 5, the combined coefficient of variation of shape CV_{shape} according to Formula 6 and the coefficient of variation of angles $CV(\angle)$ according to Formula 7.

$$H_{centerdist} = - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k \times \log_2 p_k}{N}$$

Formula 4 Entropy in information theory.

p - frequency of occurrence of the k -th unique value of $d_{(ij)}$.

N - number of elements (rectangles) in the composition

$$CV_{distance} = \frac{SD_{distance}}{M_{distance}}$$

Formula 5. coefficient of variation of the distance between the centers of pairs of rectangles in the composition.

$SD_{distance}$ - standard deviation of the distance d_{ij}

$M_{distance}$ - arithmetic mean of distance d_{ij}

$$CV_{shape} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{SD_{width}}{M_{width}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{SD_{height}}{M_{height}}\right)^2}$$

Formula 6 Combined coefficient of variation of the shape of the rectangles in the composition.

SD_{width} , SD_{height} - standard deviation of width, height of rectangles

M_{width} , M_{height} - arithmetic mean of width, height of rectangles

$$CV_{angle} = \frac{SD_{angle}}{M_{angle}}$$

Formula 7. coefficient of variation of angles between the connections of the centers of pairs of nearest rectangles.

$SD_{(angl) (e)}$ - standard deviation of the angles between the connections of centers

$M_{(angl) (e)}$ - arithmetic mean of the angles between the connections of centers

In the final step, the script calculates seven proprietary metric weighted entropy indices (defined by Formula 8-14), based on the original $H_{centerdist}$ index (Malewczyk, 2025).

These indices use the weighting of the variation in distance ($CD_{distance}$), from which the $H_{centerdist}$ index is calculated, the variation in the proportion of rectangles (CV_{shape}) in the compositional formula, and the variation in the angles (CV_{angle}) formed by lines connecting the centers of adjacent rectangles

$$SVE_D = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{distance}$$

Formula 8. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of these distances.

$$SVE_S = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{shape}$$

Formula 9. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of the dimensions of the rectangles.

$$SVE_A = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{angle}$$

Formula 10. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of the angles between the lines connecting the centers of adjacent rectangles.

$$SVE_{DS} = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{distance} \times CV_{shape}$$

Formula 11. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of these distances and the variation of the dimensions of the rectangles.

$$SVE_{DA} = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{distance} \times CV_{angle}$$

Formula 12. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of those distances and the variation of the angles between the lines connecting the centers of adjacent rectangles.

$$SVE_{SA} = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{shape} \times CV_{angle}$$

Formula 13. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of the dimensions of the rectangles and the variation of the angles between the lines connecting the centers of adjacent rectangles.

$$SVE_{DSA} = H_{centerdist} \times CV_{distance} \times CV_{shape} \times CV_{angle}$$

Formula 14. The metric entropy of the distances of the centers of adjacent rectangles, weighted by the variation of the distances, the variation of the dimensions of the

rectangles, and the variation of the angles between the lines connecting the centers of adjacent rectangles.

Statistical analyses

In the original study, the Pearson correlation between the analyzed index and the REG value within each of the 49 groups was determined. Finally, the mean r-score, Pearson's correlation coefficient, was determined.

In the study described in this manuscript, it was decided to calculate the mean Spearman correlation coefficient, perform a rank concordance analysis and determine the sum of squares of rank differences. A change in the methodology of statistical analyses was decided because the REG coefficient is a categorical variable and not an interval variable, while the coefficients analyzed are interval variables and the differences between them may not be proportional to the differences between the ranks of the REG coefficient. Statistical analyses were performed through a Python script and run in Blender through the built-in Python interpreter.

Research Quality Control and Its Replication

To verify the script's correctness, functionality from the original version was retained - visualizing the connections of the centers of the nearest rectangles. Visualization of the angles formed by the lines connecting the centers of the nearest rectangles was also added. The experiment was conducted three times, obtaining the same results each time. The final version did not encounter any errors in the script's operation. All source files were made available in a public repository, allowing independent replication of the study.

Results

Analysis of five different formulas of the author's Shannon-Variance-Entropy (SVE) index showed significant differences in their ability to predict the regularity of building façade patterns. The five different weighting combinations were tested against the original $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ index (Malewczyk, 2025) in 49 composition groups, each of which contained seven patterns ranked according to the REG scale (from 1 to 7, with 1 indicating the greatest regularity and 7 indicating the greatest irregularity). Three complementary measures-Spearman's rank correlation coefficient, the percentage of correctly ordered pairs, and the sum of squares of rank differences-were used to assess the performance of the indicators. These measures were chosen to account for the ordinal nature of rank order regularity (REG) and to avoid the limitations of linear correlation assumptions (as in the case of the r-Pearson correlation coefficient).

Table 1 Summary of results of statistical analyses.

Measure	Spearman ρ	Correct Pairs (%)	Sum of Squared Rank Differences
$H_{\text{centerdist}}$.929	88.7%	5.3
SVE _D	.871	90.0%	6.9
SVE _A	.919	92.1%	4.8
SVE _S	.946	93.2%	3.3
SVE _{DS}	.940	94.4%	3.1
SVE _{DA}	.949	95.3%	2.8
SVE _{AS}	.958	96.2%	2.5
SVE _{DAS}	.964	96.8%	2.0

A comparison of the performance of the SVE coefficient variants against the original $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ coefficient is shown in Table 1. The results show that SVE_{DAS} variance weighting for distance, proportion and angles) achieves the highest performance in all statistical indicators with a Spearman correlation of .964, a correct ordering of 96.8% and the lowest sum of squares of rank differences (2.0).

Correlation of individual variance components

The analysis revealed differential effects of individual variance components on the effectiveness of the SVE index. $SVE_{(D)}$ ($\rho=.871$) weighted by distance variance (CV_{distance}) shows the lowest effectiveness, even lower than the baseline $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ index ($\rho=.929$). An aspect that was completely ignored in the original study by Malewczyk (2025) is the variability of the angles formed between the connections of the centers of adjacent rectangles. The SVE_A weighted CV_{angle} obtained a Spearman correlation coefficient of $\rho=.919$ and is clearly superior to the baseline $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ in terms of the percentage of correctly ordered pairs (92.1% vs. 88.7%). However, the most significant component is the variation in the proportion of rectangles (CV_{shape}). SVE_S , weighted by CV_{shape} obtained a Spearman correlation coefficient of $\rho=.946$.

Verification of research hypotheses

The statistical analyses performed on the data collected in the conducted study made it possible to verify both research hypotheses and at the same time answer all four research questions.

Regarding hypothesis one, which assumed that weighted metric entropy better describes the regularity of the elevation pattern than unweighted entropy, it was confirmed for some of the variants of the SVE index. The combined SVE_{DAS} index performed 3.5 points better than the baseline $H_{\text{centerdist}}$ index and ordered 8.1 % points more pairs correctly. Thus, it was shown that all aspects-variability of distances, proportions and sizes of compositional elements and angles in the connection grid-are important in regularity analysis.

The high efficiency of the SVE_{DAS} index ($\rho=.964$), the very high percentage of correctly ordered pairs (96.8%) and its simplicity indicate the great potential of this

measure as an objective function in generative algorithms. In the course of the research, such a generative tool was developed, whose mechanism of operation was based directly on the SVE_{DAS} indicator. The tool was developed as an add-on to Blender and made available under an open-source license. The tool definitions of six composition patterns created by Malewczyk, Taraszkievicz and Czyż (2022b) as a composition typology of façades of residential, multi-family buildings. The tool allows you to select the specific type of composition you want to generate (according to the pattern definition), specify the regularity by providing expected numerical values for the interval of the SVE_{DAS} index and other parameters, such as the number of windows in rows and columns, window types, distances between window rows, heights of interstory strips and other basic physical aspects. Screenshots showing the user interface in various configurations are shown in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 User interface of the developed facade composition generator.

Thus, a tool has been obtained that allows the creation of an infinite number of elevation patterns with a given value of regularity, understood precisely as the value of the SVE index, which confirms its usefulness not only as a diagnostic measure, but also as an objective function in composition algorithms.

Discussion

The analysis of SVE (Shannon Variance-Entropy) variants reveals the complexity of the perception of regularity in facade patterns and the potential of advanced measures in their quantitative description. The results confirm that although simple entropy ($H_{centerdist}$) is highly effective, its performance can be significantly improved by considering the internal variability of the pattern.

It has been shown that distance variance ($CV_{distance}$) as a standalone component not only fails to improve the accuracy of regularity description but may even worsen it. This suggests that information about the distances between elements (e.g., the centers of gravity of facade panels) does not constitute a sufficiently clear perceptual signal. This may be since local symmetry or rhythm often occur despite significant deviations from equal distances.

In turn, the variance of angles between lines connecting the centers of compositional elements, although moderately effective as a standalone component, has a strong effect when combined with other features. This points to the importance of directional relationships in pattern perception, especially in more complex and irregular arrangements. Angular differences can act as ‘visual disturbances’ of rhythm and controlling them affects the perception of order.

The strongest component was found to be the variance in the proportions of elements (CV_{shape}). Its high effectiveness, both on its own and in combination, confirms the

intuitive understanding of regularity as the repetition of forms with similar dimensions, which is consistent with previous qualitative studies on rhythm, proportion, and scale in architectural compositions.

The best results were obtained for multi-component variants, especially SVE_{DAS} , which combines all three components: distance, angle, and proportion. Each of them describes a different aspect of perception: spatial arrangement, directional relationships, and similarity of forms, which ensures high analytical resolution and the ability to capture subtle differences in the order of the composition.

The method of evaluating the effectiveness of the measures is also worth noting. The use of three indicators (Spearman's rank correlation, pair order accuracy, and sum of rank differences) allowed for a multifaceted evaluation that better reflects the nature of ordinal data and avoids overinterpretation of linear correlation.

As a result, SVEDAS can serve as an analytical tool and indicator supporting the design process. Its high consistency with expert assessments confirms its operational potential—both in the analysis of existing designs and in the automatic generation of new variants, which has been tested during the research. The algorithm, which uses the SVE_{DAS} value as a control parameter, confirmed the functionality of the formula and its usefulness in design applications. Examples of compositions generated by the algorithm are shown in Figure 4.

The ability to define regularity through numerical values or to optimize the facade design in relation to a minimum regularity index (understood as the SVE_{DAS} value) opens a new chapter in architectural aesthetics, in line with the idea of data-driven design. The key point here is that SVE_{DAS} does not describe indirect factors influencing aesthetics (such as sunlight), but aesthetics itself. By taking this index into account,

designers gain the ability to objectively compare aesthetic aspects, which can contribute to the creation of architecture that is more inclusive, sustainable, and supportive of SDG 11.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in the course of the conducted study based on the materials and method of the 2025 Malewczyk study, statistical analyses showed that the SVE_{DAS} index, that is, the metric entropy of the lengths of the connections between the centers of the compositional elements weighted by the indicators of the variation of these lengths, the angles in the grid of the connections of the centers of the compositional elements and the variation of the proportions of the compositional elements, proved to be extremely effective in predicting the visual regularity of the compositional designs. A correlation of the author's index with expert assessments of compositional regularity of more than 96% was obtained.

For nearly 97% of the pairs correctly ordered the regularity of the composition. The original $H_{centerdist}$ index (Malewczyk 2025) admittedly also achieved high results (93% correlation and 89% correctly ordered pairs), but most importantly, the new SVE_{DAS} index shows much greater sensitivity to subtle differences in regularity.

In the course of the work, an add-on for Blender was also developed to generate façade composition patterns, based on the typology of composition patterns by Malevich, Taraszkiewicz and Czyż (2022b). The add-on has the ability to generate compositions with a predefined range of SVE_{DAS} factor. Thus, the possibility of using the determined compositional regularity coefficient as an input function in façade generative algorithms was verified. Optimizing façade design for regularity promotes the goals of SDG 11 through architectural design. The optimization of regularity serves to improve

architectural aesthetics and further- supports the creation of safe, inclusive, sustainable and high-quality cities and neighborhoods.

Fig. 4 Three examples of facade compositions with a comparable degree of regularity, generated by the developed algorithm..

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